

Rainfed Areas in the Pontal Public Irrigation Project, Petrolina, Brazil: Social Inclusion and Sustainability in Public Irrigation Policies

Elijalma Augusto Beserra¹, Maria Jaciane de Almeida Campelor², Natercio Melo³, Maria Augusta Maia e Souza Beserra⁴, Emily Vitoria Maia e Souza Beserra⁵, Jaques José da Silva Souza⁶

¹Universidade Federal do Vale do São Francisco (UNIVASF), <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6445-347X>

²Universidade Federal do Vale do São Francisco (UNIVASF), <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2152-0948>

³Companhia de Desenvolvimento dos Vales do São Francisco e do Parnaíba (Codevasf), <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-8533-5460>

⁴Universidade Federal do Vale do São Francisco (UNIVASF), <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0087-099X>

⁵Faculdade de Ciências Aplicadas e Sociais de Petrolina (FACAPE), <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-0228-6772>

⁶Universidade Federal do Vale do São Francisco (UNIVASF), <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-2800-6916>

ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
19 January 2026

ABSTRACT

The Rainfed Areas of the Pontal Public Irrigation Project (PPI), located in the municipality of Petrolina, Pernambuco, represent a paradigm shift in the implementation of public irrigation projects in the Brazilian Semi-arid region. This initiative is innovative within the scope of the Public Irrigation Projects developed by the São Francisco and Parnaíba Valleys Development Company (Codevasf) and was conceived as a strategy to mitigate the social impacts resulting from the expropriation of rural properties required for the implementation of the irrigated scheme. The model is based on a differentiated land tenure, economic, and socio-environmental organization, grounded in guided land occupation, land tenure regularization, and shared institutional management. This article analyzes how the adoption of a planned socioeconomic intervention enabled the creation and consolidation of Rainfed Areas within a project originally designed for irrigated agriculture. The analysis considers the results accumulated over approximately ten years of implementation, demonstrating that, despite punctual non-compliances observed in part of the production units, the model has consolidated itself as a successful experience of social inclusion, income generation, and sustainable use of natural resources. The results indicate positive impacts on improving the living conditions of beneficiary families, diversifying productive activities, and strengthening sustainable territorial development, in line with the ONU (United Nations) 2030 Agenda and the ODS (Sustainable Development Goals), particularly SDGs 1, 2, 10, and 15. It is concluded that the replication of this model is feasible and desirable, provided it is accompanied by institutional improvements.

Corresponding Author:
Elijalma Augusto Beserra

KEYWORDS: Public Irrigation Projects; Rainfed Areas; Social inclusion; Sustainable development.

I. INTRODUCTION

The implementation of large public irrigation projects in the Brazilian Semi-Arid region has historically been associated with the promotion of regional development, especially through the expansion of the irrigated agricultural frontier, economic dynamism, and the generation of employment and income (Beserra, 2024). However, such projects have also produced significant social impacts, particularly as a result of expropriation processes, forced displacement of rural populations, and territorial reorganization. In light of this scenario, and after analyzing traumatic experiences, such as those observed in the PPI

(Public Irrigation Projects) of the Itaparica System, the São Francisco and Parnaíba Valleys Development Company (Codevasf) began to incorporate institutional strategies aimed at mitigating these impacts, seeking to reconcile productive efficiency, social justice, and environmental sustainability.

The Dryland Areas that emerged within the scope of the Pontal Sustainable Project are part of this institutional effort, having been conceived as a productive resettlement alternative for expropriated families and rural workers affected by the implementation of the Pontal Public Irrigation Project, in the municipality of Petrolina/PE. These areas, unsuitable for irrigation, were functionally integrated into the

larger project, configuring an institutional innovation by allowing the coexistence of irrigated and dryland production systems in the same territory. The selection of beneficiaries took place in a participatory manner, with indications from local communities and technical validation by Codevasf, conferring social legitimacy to the process and strengthening the feeling of territorial belonging.

The analysis of this experience directly dialogues with the approach of development as freedom, proposed by the Indian economist Amartya Sen (2010). For the author, development should not be understood only as economic growth, but as a process of expanding human capabilities and substantive freedoms. As Sen (2010) points out, “development can be seen as a process of expanding the real freedoms that people enjoy” (Sen, 2010, p. 16). From this perspective, access to land, production, public policies, and institutional participation constitutes a central element for expanding the capabilities of family farmers, especially in contexts of socioeconomic vulnerability, such as the Brazilian Semi-Arid region.

Ricardo Abramovay (2015) contributes to this analysis by emphasizing that sustainable development in rural areas depends on strengthening local actors and valuing the social and institutional dimensions of the economy. According to the author, “development is not limited to increasing income, but to the ability of societies to create institutional environments that expand the possibilities of choice for individuals” (Abramovay, 2015, p. 37). Thus, experiences such as the Dryland Area of the Pontal PPI demonstrate that public policies can promote social inclusion when they recognize family farming as a strategic subject of territorial development.

In the same vein, Caporal et al. (2009), Caporal and Costabeber (2004) highlight that sustainability in rural areas must be understood in a multidimensional way, articulating environmental, economic, social, cultural and political aspects. For Caporal (2009), agroecology and the strengthening of family farming represent fundamental paths for the construction of fairer and more sustainable rural development models, especially in semi-arid regions. As the author points out, “there is no possible sustainability without the protagonism of farmers in the construction of productive strategies compatible with their territories” (Caporal, 2009, p. 89).

Methodologically, this study adopts a qualitative-quantitative approach, of an exploratory and analytical-descriptive nature, based on the documentary analysis of institutional regulations of Codevasf, especially those related to AO (Occupation Authorizations), as well as technical reports, administrative records and secondary data on the Pontal PPI. Additionally, field observations and information systematization were carried out with the beneficiaries of the Dryland Areas, allowing for an understanding of the

productive, social, and institutional dynamics over approximately ten years of project implementation.

The results indicate that, despite occasional nonconformities in some of the parcel units, mainly related to the legal fragility of the Occupation Authorizations and the limitations of continuous technical assistance, the Dryland Farming model has consolidated itself as a success story, a successful experience of social inclusion of workers linked to family farming, income generation and sustainable use of natural resources. As a result of the data collected during the study, it is possible to observe an improvement in the living conditions of the beneficiary families, diversification of productive strategies and strengthening of inclusive territorial development (Rigotto et al., 2016), liberating and socio-economically and environmentally sustainable.

In light of Sen's (2010) capabilities approach, the institutional contributions of Abramovay (2015) and Beserra (2024), as well as the agroecological perspective of Caporal et al. (2009) and Caporal and Costabeber (2004), it is concluded that the adoption of the plot system of the Dryland Areas of the Pontal PPI contributes to the expansion of the real freedoms of family farmers, by creating material, institutional and social conditions that broaden their autonomy and capacity for choice. This experience directly dialogues with the SDG's (Sustainable Development Goals) of the 2030 Agenda of the United Nations, especially SDG 1 (No Poverty), SDG 2 (Zero Hunger and Sustainable Agriculture), SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities) and SDG 15 (Life on Land).

It is concluded that the replication of the model adopted by Codevasf within the scope of the Dryland Areas of the Pontal PPI proved to be viable, inclusive, sustainable and desirable, reinforcing the importance of public irrigation policies guided not only by productive efficiency, but also by social justice and sustainability. Therefore, it is essential that such actions be accompanied by institutional improvements, continuous technical assistance, and greater legal balance between beneficiaries and the State.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study is characterized as a mixed-methods (qualitative and quantitative) research, exploratory, descriptive, and analytical in nature, according to the methodological assumptions of Lakatos (2021), Minayo (2017), and Marconi and Lakatos (2003). The investigation was conducted in order to highlight the processes of participation and cooperation between technicians from the Codevasf, family farmers, and rural workers involved in the implementation of the Dryland Areas of the PPI.

The study area corresponds to the southern portion of the Pontal - PPI, located in the rural area of the municipality of Petrolina, State of Pernambuco, between the geographic coordinates 8°55'39.66”S and 40°38'13.39”W (northern

limit) and 9°07'33.20"S and 40°25'47.45"W (southern limit) (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – View of location of the Pontal - PPI, Petrolina/PE.

Source: CODEVASF (2023)

Data collection occurred in a structured and continuous manner, through semi-structured interviews, participant observation, document analysis, photographic and audiovisual records, and bibliographic research, in accordance with the methodological steps proposed by Marconi and Lakatos (2003) and the precepts of NBR 6022 (ABNT, 2018). The documentary research included institutional regulations, technical reports, legal opinions, technical notes, internal resolutions, and empirical data produced by Codevasf technicians, in addition to documents. The information contained in Administrative Process N°. 59530.000565/2011-11 (Codevasf, 2011), accessed pursuant to Law N°. 12.527/2011 (Access to Information Law) (BRAZIL, 2011).

The legal framework is based primarily on Law N°. 12.787/2013 - Irrigation Law (BRAZIL, 2013), Law N°. 11.326/2006 - Family Farming Law (BRAZIL, 2006), the Occupation Standard for Public Irrigation Projects – NOR-501 (Codevasf, 2011), and opinions from the Legal Department of Codevasf.

From a methodological point of view, the study adopts an inductive-deductive approach, with a predominance of the inductive method (Sampieri; Collado; Lúcio, 2013), based on the analysis of the institutional and operational specificities of the Non-Irrigable Parcel Units of the Pontal PPI, seeking to construct general inferences that can support future experiences in public policies for irrigation and territorial development.

A. Contextualization and Conception of the Pontal Project of the Dryland Area

The Pontal Dryland Program, responsible for the design of Non-Irrigable Parcel Units, was established in 2009 with the objective of mitigating the social impacts resulting from the expropriations carried out for the implementation of the Pontal Irrigated Project, the initial phase of the PPI, as well as promoting the productive and rational use of areas unsuitable for irrigation. It is an institutional response to the limitations observed in previous experiences of public irrigation projects in the São Francisco Valley, marked by processes of population displacement and weakening of territorial ties.

According to the Codevasf, the Pontal PPI is a project aimed at utilizing areas of soil suitable for irrigated agriculture in the municipality of Petrolina/PE, using the São Francisco River as its water source. The project encompasses two contiguous areas, Pontal Norte and Pontal Sul, physically separated by the Pontal stream. The total area of the development corresponds to 33,526 hectares, of which 6,571 hectares are designated as a legal reserve. Soil studies indicated that only 7,717 hectares are suitable for irrigation due to drainage limitations and soil salinity.

The southern portion of the Pontal PPI comprises an area of 18,952.14 hectares, subdivided into irrigable areas, rainfed areas, collective pastures, legal reserve, and common-use infrastructure. The irrigable area occupies approximately 3,510 hectares, distributed among 297 UPF (Family Production Units), with an average area of 6 hectares per plot, and 37 UPE (Business Production Units), with areas ranging from 21 to 74 hectares. Of the areas not intended for irrigation, approximately 7,000 hectares were allocated to the Pontal Sequeiro Project, organized into 140 plots with an average area of 50 hectares, in addition to six units called "green lungs," totaling 72 hectares, currently benefiting 139 families selected based on social and productive criteria (Figure 2).

Figure 2 – Areas of the Pontal PPI, Petrolina/PE.

Source: CODEVASF (2023)

“Rainfed Areas in the Pontal Public Irrigation Project, Petrolina, Brazil: Social Inclusion and Sustainability in Public Irrigation Policies”

The conception of the Dryland Area was influenced by historical experiences marked by negative social impacts, such as the resettlements resulting from the Sobradinho and Itaparica dams and the conflicts associated with the implementation of the Bebedouro PPI (Integrated Planning Project). The project foresaw the land reorganization of non-irrigable areas and the provision of basic infrastructure, including water supply, electricity, rural roads, and irrigated collective pastures for forage production. The AO, formalized in December 2012 with an initial term of five years, were configured as precarious legal instruments, whose lack of systematic renewal, after more than 13 years, has increased the legal insecurity of the occupants, with potential social, productive and territorial repercussions.

Source: BESERRA (2025)

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The institutional experience of Codevasf in implementing PPI's has historically been oriented towards prioritizing the use of soil patches considered suitable for irrigation. Regarding the method adopted by Codevasf for the establishment of PPIs, Castro et al. (2013) describe that PPIs "are areas that the public authorities expropriate, compensating the owners, and in which they develop sizing and feasibility studies to assemble the irrigation canals" (Castro et al., 2013, p. 269). Furthermore, according to Castro et al. (2013), after the assembly of the common PPI structures, it is up to the farmer who receives a plot to "assemble an irrigation system" (Castro et al., 2013, p. 269).

As can be observed, the technical and administrative decisions adopted by the public company, when preparing the projects for the implementation of the PPI's focus on the anthropological basis of maximizing irrigated agricultural production, through the dimensioning of hydraulic and irrigation systems aimed exclusively at this purpose. This orientation can be observed in the Public Irrigation Projects of Bebedouro, Senador Nilo Coelho and Maria Tereza in Petrolina/PE, as well as in the projects of Mandacaru and, later, Maniçoba, Curaçá, Tourão and Salitre in Juazeiro/BA.

According to the regulations in force at the time of the implementation of these projects, the dryland areas included in the irrigated perimeters were considered restricted use spaces, and initiatives aimed at their productive use were prohibited. Even when located in areas contiguous to the irrigable units, any expressions of interest were systematically rejected (Figure 3).

Figure 3 – Harmonious arrangement between irrigated area and pig farming in the Pernambuco region.

This logic was anchored in a technocratic conception of territorial planning, strongly influenced by the paradigm of agricultural modernization, which prioritized productive efficiency and control of production factors, to the detriment of pre-existing social and economic dynamics in the territory (Cavalcanti et al., 2014; Cazella; Bonnal; Maluf, 2009).

The central premise that supported this restriction was based on the hypothesis that the eventual future irrigation of rainfed areas could compromise water availability, originally dimensioned for a previously defined irrigable area. However, this understanding has been progressively revised based on technological advances in irrigation systems, which have enabled greater efficiency in water use and a significant reduction in the volumes needed for agricultural production. This process of technical revision opened space for the reinterpretation of the productive potential of rainfed areas, in line with more integrated approaches to rural development.

With regard to the acquisition of land intended for the implementation of the projects, it is observed that, in several cases, there was an interruption of historically consolidated local production systems, notably those associated with the extensive breeding of goats and sheep. These activities played a central role in the economy and social reproduction of rural families in the semi-arid region. This disruption highlights the limitations of public policies conceived in a top-down manner, with low incorporation of local knowledge and traditional strategies for living with the semi-arid environment, as pointed out by Caporal et al. (2009), Caporal and Costabeber (2004).

In light of the capabilities and inclusive and sustainable development approach proposed by Amartya Sen (2010), such processes can be interpreted as restrictive to the expansion of the substantive freedoms of the social subjects involved, insofar as they reduced the possibilities of choice and continuity of historically constructed ways of life. In this sense, development cannot be understood solely as an increase in production or income, but as the expansion of

“Rainfed Areas in the Pontal Public Irrigation Project, Petrolina, Brazil: Social Inclusion and Sustainability in Public Irrigation Policies”

individual and collective capacities to decide on the use of the territory and available resources.

Specifically in the Pontal PPI, the paradigm shift resulted in the decision to allocate approximately 7,000 hectares, not incorporated into the Irrigable Parcel Units, to the initial constitution of 140 Dryland Parcel Units, a fact that represents a significant inflection in the traditional logic of irrigation projects. By prioritizing the settlement of families from the area covered by the expropriation decree, respecting previously defined criteria, this initiative signals an approximation with conceptions of territorial development that recognize the productive and social diversity of rural space (Cazella; Bonnal; Maluf, 2009; Zimmermann, 2014). This strategy, albeit in its early stages, engages with perspectives advocated by Cavalcanti (2014), considering the territory not only as a physical support for production, but also as a space for life, social relations, and the construction of identities.

A. Agroecological actions

The results demonstrate that the Pontal Sequeiro project should be understood as an eminently extension-oriented action, structured from systematic processes of training and technical support for approximately 350 families affected by the expropriation process and residing in the vicinity of the Pontal Project. The strategies adopted were guided by an exploitation model based on agroecological principles, with an emphasis on diversified production systems, aiming at reducing the climatic and economic risks associated with crops and livestock, as well as promoting incremental changes in technological adoption patterns, prioritizing process technologies over product technologies (Figure 4).

Figure 4 – Dryland area with agroecological system em Pernambuco - PE.

Source: BESERRA (2025)

Among the main actions conducted by the technical assistance team, the following stood out: technological and managerial training of farmers, evaluation and improvement

of the social and professional organization of producers, in addition to carrying out participatory diagnoses of the production units, which supported the formulation, monitoring and evaluation of improvement plans. Other relevant initiatives involved the implementation of collective production and processing units, the development of integration models with anchor companies and other strategic partners, the implementation of alternative production and income generation programs with a gender approach, as well as the consolidation of a contextualized education program aimed at young people, in conjunction with local schools.

The training and capacity-building services for farmers in Pontal Sequeiro began in 2009. However, with the interruption of the ATER (Technical Assistance and Rural Extension) contract in 2015, due to budgetary constraints of the Federal Government, the proposed model could not be fully completed or validated. This discontinuity occurred in a context marked by multiple structural weaknesses, such as delays in formalizing access to land and credit, delays in the implementation of basic infrastructure (electricity and water points), as well as obstacles related to environmental licensing.

It is worth highlighting that the ATER service had an approximate annual cost of R\$ 1.7 million and that the most consistent results could only be measured from the end of 2012, when farmers began to have land ownership documents.

Even so, some relevant results could be observed, such as the fact that producers, organized into interest groups, began to produce and market goats and sheep with better zootechnical standards, reducing the slaughter age to about eight months, compared to the 18 to 24 months traditionally observed. As well as the production of curd cheese from goat's milk, carried out in a collective cheese factory installed in an adapted building, but equipped with hygiene standards compatible with obtaining a license from the state sanitary inspection agency.

The interest group focused on umbu extraction deserves special mention. They began to market the fruit both fresh and in the form of processed products in a small, adapted agro-industry, including sweets, jams, pulps, and mousses. Composed mostly of women, this group obtained, in 2014, an approximate per capita income of R\$ 2,000.00 in less than 80 working days, an amount higher than that received in a year of participation in the Bolsa Família Program. Agro-industrial and extractive activities contributed to increasing the share of these sources in the overall income composition of the production units.

With a view to expanding the economic results of these initiatives, the level of social organization of the producers was strengthened, culminating in the creation of the Coopontal (Agricultural and Extractive Development Cooperative of Pontal), composed of 40 members. The

cooperative began operating in both the marketing of Pontal products in public and private institutional markets (mini-markets, fairs, bakeries and events) and in the provision of agricultural mechanization services.

The creation of Coopontal represented a significant organizational advance, expanding access to institutional and private markets. Studies indicate that the average monthly income of producers practically doubled between 2012 and 2014, even in the face of severe climatic restrictions.

Even more promising prospects were associated with the implementation of plans to improve agro-industrial units, previously agreed upon with public support programs, such as Prorural-PE, the APL of the Ministry of Integration and Senai/Sebrae, including civil works and the acquisition of complementary equipment for the cheese factory and for a new umbu processing unit.

These actions contributed to a gradual increase in producers' income. The average gross margin per producer evolved from a level equivalent to 0.88 monthly minimum wages in 2012 to 1.80 monthly minimum wages in 2014. Goat and sheep farming for meat production remained the main income-generating activity in the area surrounding Pontal, with an estimated value of R\$ 2.9 million, corresponding to approximately 73% of the total agricultural and extractive revenue in 2014.

Thus, the performance of Pontal Sequeiro can be considered highly satisfactory, especially when considering the limitations inherent in a technical assistance program aimed at family farmers in the initial phase of exploiting their plots, located in areas with low agricultural suitability soils, with still restricted access to Pronaf credit and simultaneously facing the worst drought recorded in the Brazilian semi-arid region in the last 40 years. Future prospects appeared positive, also based on non-financial advances that had been progressively observed.

The importance of ATER can be seen in the production data presented for the period between 2009 and 2015, when there was systematic technical monitoring. The Pontal Project Dryland Area showed significant results. Highlights include the strengthening of goat and sheep farming, the implementation of collective agro-industries, such as goat milk cheese production, and the development of umbu extraction, with female leadership and significant income generation.

B. current situation and critical points

It is noted that with the expiration of the AO's in 2017, and the subsequent approval of a draft for renewal through Resolution N°. 889/2019 of the Executive Board of Codevasf (Codevasf, 2019), it became necessary to carry out a new survey to investigate irregularities. Of the 139 subdivided units, it was found that 80 were in compliance

with the AO, while 56 presented irregularities or a situation pending verification.

The main infractions identified included irregular alienation of lots, planting of fruit trees in dryland areas, irregular water withdrawals, and non-direct exploitation of the area by the beneficiary. For such cases, the Commission recommended the adoption of administrative measures provided for in Law N°. 12,787/2013, always preceded by notification and an opportunity for regularization, prioritizing the adoption of solutions that allow for sustainable development (Sen, 2010) and coexistence with the problems generated by drought, providing means to promote the development not only of agribusiness, but also of small farmers, mitigating inequality and "the dominance of the land structure by national and multinational companies" (Rigotto et al., 2016).

C. Aspects of the current situation of the PPI

Despite the irregularities found, these do not compromise the continuity of the Pontal Project, a rainfed area. On the contrary, they highlight the need to strengthen institutional governance, resume technical assistance, and update the legal instruments of occupation. Experience shows that the lack of continuous monitoring has contributed to the emergence of distortions, without, however, invalidating the original objectives of the project.

The uniqueness of the AOs in the context of a PPI requires compliance with the specific legal regime of the Irrigation Law, Law N°. 12,787, of January 11, 2013, which provides for the National Irrigation Policy (BRAZIL, 2013), especially with regard to eviction procedures, which should prioritize regularization and not simply the repossession of the area.

This reinforces the Pontal Project's aim to promote the productive and social inclusion of family farmers in a context marked by climatic and historical limitations on land access. In this sense, the eviction procedures associated with the project should prioritize land and productive regularization, not simply the retaking of areas, recognizing the social function performed by the families who produce and reside there. The adoption of regularization mechanisms, combined with technical assistance and productive organization, contributes to the socioeconomic stability of rural communities, strengthens activities adapted to the semi-arid region, such as small ruminant livestock farming, forage production, extraction of native species, and the reduction of land conflicts. Thus, the emphasis on regularization, instead of merely coercive eviction, consolidates the project as an instrument for sustainable development, social inclusion, and dignified permanence of the farmer in the territory.

All hypertext links and section bookmarks will be removed from papers during the processing of papers for publication. If you need to refer to an Internet email address

or URL in your paper, you must type out the address or URL fully in Regular font.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of the Dryland Areas of the Pontal PPI (Public Irrigation Project) shows that this experience has consolidated itself as an innovative, socially relevant, and territorially situated public policy. By articulating the mitigation of social impacts resulting from expropriation processes, the promotion of local economic development (Beserra, 2020), and the adoption of environmentally sustainable production practices, Pontal Sequeiro demonstrates that it is possible to broaden the scope of public privacy projects beyond conventional irrigated agriculture, incorporating production models adapted to the social and environmental specificities of the Pernambuco Semi-Arid region.

As shown throughout the article, the results obtained confirm the hypothesis that the combination of ATER, social organization, and the adoption of agroecological principles constitute a strategic vector for sustainable territorial development. In light of the development as capacity expansion approach proposed by Amartya Sen (2010), it is observed that the advances were not limited to increased income, but involved broader processes of strengthening the substantive freedoms of farming families, such as access to land, production, collective organization, decision-making, and market access.

The production systems developed in the Rainfed Areas, with emphasis on goat and sheep farming for meat and milk production, umbu extraction, artisanal-based agro-industrialization, and low-water-demand fruit growing, demonstrated the abundance of LPA (Local Productive Arrangements) that were exploited and resilient, adapted to the edaphoclimatic conditions of the Semi-Arid region. These results reinforce a conception of multidimensional rural development, which articulates social inclusion, productive autonomy, and environmental sustainability, in line with the SDG's of the 2030 Agenda, especially SDG 1 (No Poverty), SDG 2 (Zero Hunger and Sustainable Agriculture), SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities), and SDG 15 (Life on Land).

Furthermore, the study results highlight the centrality of ATER as a structuring public policy, especially when guided by participatory methodologies and an agroecological perspective. The creation and strengthening of collective organizations, such as Coopontal, as well as the empowering protagonism of women and young people in productive and agro-industrial activities, indicate that the impacts of Pontal Sequeiro have gone beyond the economic dimension, reaching social, institutional, and symbolic spheres of territorial development. These processes directly relate to the expansion of individual and collective

capacities, as advocated by Sen (2010), by favoring the exercise of autonomy, cooperation, and social participation.

However, the identified institutional weaknesses, especially the interruption of ATER services, limitations in land regularization, restricted access to credit, precarious basic infrastructure, and obstacles related to environmental limits, compromise the full consolidation of the model. These specifications show that public policies for territorial development are maintained in a continuous, progressive, inter-institutional manner and with long-term commitments, otherwise the expansion of the capacities and freedoms they intend to promote will be restricted.

Even in the face of these challenges, and in a context marked by severe estimation events in the Brazilian Semi-Arid region, the socioeconomic indicators of occurrence allow us to classify the performance of Pontal Sequeiro as highly overwhelming. The increase in the average income of families, the improvement in the quality of products, the insertion in institutional and private markets, and the strengthening of the local productive base give empirical robustness to the results presented.

It is concluded, therefore, that the continuity and improvement of the Dryland Areas of the Pontal PPI are not only viable, but strategic for the formulation of more inclusive and sustainable public policies for inspection and rural development. Provided that they accompany the improvement of legal instruments, the clarification of Codevasf's responsibilities in Occupation Authorizations, the systematic resumption of ATER, and the strengthening of institutional dialogue with beneficiaries, such experiences can contribute significantly to expanding the capacities of family farmers and to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals in the Brazilian Semi-Arid region..

REFERENCES

1. ABRAMOVAY, Ricardo. Sustainable development, ethical values and worldviews. Valor Econômico, São Paulo, December 1, 2015.
2. Brazilian Association of Technical Standards. NBR 6022: Information and documentation – Article in a scientific periodical publication. Rio de Janeiro: ABNT, 2018.
3. BESERRA, E. A. Changes in the socioeconomic conditions of the Bebedouro Public Irrigation Project after 50 years of its implementation: analysis of the discourse of the actors involved. 2020. Dissertation (Professional Master's in Rural Extension) – Federal University of the São Francisco Valley, Campus Espaço Plural, Juazeiro, BA, 2020.
4. BESERRA, Eljalma Augusto et al. Corporate Social Responsibility of Irrigated Fruit Farming Companies in the Sertão of Pernambuco: The Case

“Rainfed Areas in the Pontal Public Irrigation Project, Petrolina, Brazil: Social Inclusion and Sustainability in Public Irrigation Policies”

- of Agrodan. *Revista Veritas de Difusão Científica*, v. 5, n. 3, p. 531-562, 2024.
5. BRAZIL. Law N°. 11,326, of July 24, 2006. Establishes the guidelines for the National Policy on Family Farming. Official Gazette of the Union: Brasília, 2006. Available at: https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_ato2004-2006/2006/lei/111326.htm. Accessed on: September 21, 2025.
 6. BRAZIL. Law N°. 12,787, of January 11, 2013. Provides for the National Irrigation Policy. Official Gazette of the Union: Brasília, 2013. Available at: https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_ato2011-2014/2013/lei/112787.htm. Accessed on: September 20, 2025.
 7. BRAZIL. Law N°. 12,527, of November 18, 2011. Provides for access to information as stipulated in item XXXIII of article 5, item II of paragraph 3 of article 37 and paragraph 2 of article 216 of the Federal Constitution. Official Gazette of the Union: Brasília, 2011. Available at: https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_ato2011-2014/2011/lei/112527.htm. Accessed on: September 20, 2025.
 8. CASTRO, Luciano Thomé. et al. Organizational models for public-private partnerships in public irrigation in Brazil. *Revista de Administração*, São Paulo, v. 48, n. 2, Apr./May/June, p. 268-280. 2013. Available at: <https://www.scielo.br/j/rausp/a/xJgzRth7Y9htsDjMh3rd/?format=pdf&lang=pt>. Accessed on: Oct. 10, 2025.
 9. CAPORAL, Francisco Roberto (Ed.) et al. *Agroecology: a science of the field of complexity*. Brasília: Embrapa Informação Tecnológica, 2009. 111 p.
 10. CAPORAL, Francisco Roberto; COSTABEBER, José Antônio. *Agroecology and sustainable rural development: perspectives for a new rural extension*. Porto Alegre: UFRGS, 2004.
 11. CAVALCANTI, Josefa Salete Barbosa et al. *Participation, Territory and Citizenship: a look at territorial development policy in Brazil*. Recife: Editora Universitária da UFPE, 2014. DOI: 10.1590/S0103-40141997000100005. Available at: <https://www.scielo.br/j/ea/a/TFfJ9rnn5cDpqqFpryxWtnN/?format=html&lang=pt>. Accessed on: November 17, 2025.
 12. CAZELLA, Ademir Antonio; BONNAL, Philippe; MALUF, Renato S. *Family farming: multifunctionality and territorial development in Brazil*. Mauad X Ed., 2009. 301 p. ISBN 978-85-7478-292-8. Available at: <https://wp.ufpel.edu.br/consagro/files/2011/08/CAZELLA-BONNAL-MALUF-Agricultura-Familiar-Multifuncionalidade.pdf>. Accessed on: November 18, 2025.
 13. CODEVASF. *Occupation Standard for Public Irrigation Projects – NOR-501*. Brasília: Codevasf, 2011.
 14. CODEVASF. Resolution N°. 889, of December 18, 2019. Executive Board. Brasília: Codevasf, 2019.
 15. CODEVASF. Administrative Process N°. 59530.000565/2011-11. Petrolina: Codevasf, 2011.
 16. LAKATOS, Eva Maria. *Fundamentals of Scientific Methodology*. Rio de Janeiro: Atlas, 2021. Ebook. ISBN 9788597026580. Available at: <https://integrada.minhabiblioteca.com.br/#/books/9788597026580>.
 17. MARCONI, Marina de Andrade; LAKATOS, Eva Maria. *Fundamentals of scientific methodology*. 5th ed. São Paulo: Atlas, 2003.
 18. MINAYO, Maria Cecília de Souza. *Scientificity, generalization and dissemination of qualitative studies*. *Ciência & Saúde Coletiva*, Rio de Janeiro, v. 22, n. 1, p. 16. 17, 2017.
 19. RIGOTTO, R. M. et al. *Irrigated perimeters and violated rights in Ceará and Rio Grande do Norte: “Why does the water arrive and we have to leave?”*. *Pegada Magazine*, v. 17, n. 2, Dec. p. 122-144. 2016.
 20. SAMPIERI, R. H.; COLLADO, C. F.; LUCIO, M. D. P. B. *Research methodology*. 5th ed. Porto Alegre: Penso, 2013.
 21. ZIMMERMANN, Silvia Aparecida; GRISA, Catia; TECCHIO, Andréia; LEITE, Sérgio Pereira; BONNAL, Philippe; CAZELLA, Ademir Antônio; DELGADO, Nelson Giordano; MALUF, Renato Jamil; MATTEI, Lauro. *Territorial development and policies to combat rural poverty in Brazil*. *Revista Campo-Território*, Uberlândia, v. 9, n. 17 Apr., p. 540–573, 2014. DOI: 10.14393/RCT91723828. Available at: <https://seer.ufu.br/index.php/campoterritorio/article/view/23828>. Accessed on: Oct. 28, 2025.